

RESOURCE PRODUCTIVITY AND RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY IN BUFFALO MILK PRODUCTION IN BEED DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to find out resource productivity and resource use efficiency in buffalo milk production in Beed district of Maharashtra. By adopting multistage random sampling 60 milk producer were selected from 12 villages. The selected milk producers were classified as small, medium and large, according to their land holding. Simple statistical approaches can be used to look at the milk producer's usage behavior and assess resource use efficiency. In case of human labour MVP to price ratio was 3.50 indicated underutilization of resource. At overall level, the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.65 which shows that the explanatory variables in the model were responsible for 65 per cent of the variation in milk output. In overall, the concentrate, human labour and medicine cost regression coefficients were found to be significant, but the dry fodder and green fodder regression coefficient was found to be non-significant. The sum of regression coefficient was (0.0838) which indicated decreasing return to scale.

Key words: Buffalo, Cobb-Douglas, Resource use efficiency, Regression coefficient

Introduction

Livestock sector plays pivotal role in providing nutritive food rich, in animal protein and also helps in supplementing family incomes and generating gainful employment in the rural sector. Buffalo milk is great for healthy bones, dental health and cardiovascular health. In buffalo milk 6-7 per cent fat, 9 per cent SNF (Solids Not Fat), proteins, lactose and ash content are 4.52 per cent, 4.45 per cent, 0.80 per cent respectively. Total Buffalo Population in the country is 109.85 million during 2019. Total Buffalo has increased by 1.1 per cent over previous Livestock Census (2012). Female Buffalo Population increased by 8.61 per cent whereas Male Buffalo is declined by 42.35 per cent over previous census. About 20.5 per cent of the total livestock is contributed by buffaloes. Milch buffalo population has increased marginally by 0.2 per cent over previous census in which in-milk has increased by 4.3 per cent whereas dry category has declined by 10.2 per cent. Buffalo population in Maharashtra state is 5.6 million. The data revealed that the livestock population in India has grown by 4.6 per cent from 512 M in 2012 to about 536 M in 2019. (Source: 20th livestock census 2019).

Materials and Methods

For the study year 2020-21 information was collected from respondents through face-to-face interview. Beed district was purposively selected because it is well known for milk production in the Aurangabad region of Maharashtra state & Beed rank second in milch animal population in Aurangabad division. Three tehsils Kaij, Ambajogai and Parali were purposively selected on the basis of buffalo population. The list of farmers having buffalo were prepared from twelve selected villages and from each village 5 farmers were selected randomly. Thus, in all 60 Farmers having buffalo milk production enterprise were selected. The selected

farmer was categorized on the basis of land holding viz; small (up to 1-2 ha), medium (2-4 ha) and large (4 ha & above).

Statistical tools applied: Production function approach

Results and Discussion**Resource productivity and resource use efficiency in dairy enterprises.**

The overall buffalo on the chosen farms was 102. From that Table, 44 buffaloes in small size group and 58 buffalo in medium size group were all being raised by sample farmers. Due to the high milk yield, the buffalo regression model was found to be significant. As a result, the Cobb-Douglas production function was fitted to assess the resource productivity and resource use efficiency with regard to the production of buffalo milk, and the results are shown in Table 1.

Regression coefficient of functional analysis for buffalo milk production

In table 1 at overall level, the regression coefficient for concentrate (X_3) was 0.039 and medicine cost (X_5) was 0.013 which were significant at the 10% level and positive. The regression coefficient for human labour (X_4) was 0.101 which was highly significant at 1% level and positive. It implied that a 1% increase in the use of concentrate would result in 1% rise in milk output. However, the regression coefficient of other variable like dry fodder (X_2) and green fodder (X_1) were non-significant. It means 1 per cent increase in use of dry fodder and green fodder would lead to decrease milk production by 1 per cent. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.65 which shown that 65 per cent variation in overall buffalo milk production was explained because of (independent) variables included in model. The sum of regression coefficient was (0.0838) which indicated decreasing return to scale.

Table 1: Regression coefficient of log linear function in buffalo milk production

Independent variable	Regression coefficient (bi)	Overall Standard error of bi	t value
Green fodder (X_1)	-0.021	0.053	-0.40
Dry fodder (X_2)	-0.048	0.034	-1.41
Concentrate (X_3)	0.039	0.022	1.777*
Human labour (X_4)	0.101	0.027	3.748***
Medicine cost (X_5)	0.013	0.0157	0.841*

Return to scale ($\sum bi$) = 0.0838

Intercept = 7.15

F value = 7.69***

 $R^2 = 0.65$

*** denotes 1 per cent significant level, ** denotes 5 per cent significant level and *denotes 10 per cent significant level.

1.2 Marginal value productivity and resource use efficiency in buffalo milk production.

At the geometric mean level of the corresponding input and output, the marginal value productivity (MVP) of independent variables in the fitted equation for buffalo milk production was calculated. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 2. The ratio between

marginal value productivity and factor price of the respective variables was then calculated to determine resource use efficiency.

In regard to resource use efficiency, from Table 2 that, in case of human labour MVP to price ratio was 3.50 indicated under utilization of resource. The resource use efficiency analysis further showed that green fodder dry fodder, concentrate and medicine cost were used in excess, which increases cost of milk production. Therefore, to

maximize the profit from buffalo milk production, the farmers in study area have to reallocate the available resources.

Table.2 Resource use efficiency in buffalo milk production for overall

Resources	GM	MPP	MVP	Factor price (PX)	MVP/PX	Level of resource use
Green fodder (X ₁)	3579.51	-0.00933	-0.03731	4	-0.00933	Excess
Dry fodder (X ₂)	1631.97	-0.04592	-0.13775	3	-0.04592	Excess
Concentrate (X ₃)	661.88	0.091349	1.187542	13	0.091349	Excess
Human labour (X ₄)	44.8	3.500124	700.0249	200	3.500124	Under
Medicine cost (X ₅)	513.34	0.039982	0.103954	2.6	0.039982	Excess

(Geometric mean of Y = 1544)

(Price of output =60)

Conclusion

The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.78 which shown that 78 per cent variation in overall buffalo milk production was explained because of (independent) variables included in model. The sum of regression coefficient was (0.0838) which indicated decreasing return to scale. The resource use efficiency analysis further showed that green fodder dry fodder, concentrate and medicine cost were used in excess, which increases cost of milk production. Therefore, to maximize the profit from buffalo milk production, the farmers in study area have to reallocate the available resources.

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